

Synthesis of Bridgmanite Using a Multi-Anvil Apparatus

1. Starting Material

- (1) I1565-1:** 1 mol MgSiO_3 + 0.05 mol MgO + 5 wt.% H_2O . The water was introduced via $\text{Mg}(\text{OH})_2$. Pure powders of SiO_2 , MgO , and $\text{Mg}(\text{OH})_2$ (purities >99.9%, Alfa Aesar ®) were mixed accordingly.
- (2) S7573:** 10 wt.% CaCO_3 (99.99% purity, Alfa Aesar ®) + 90 wt.% natural HNB peridotite [SiO_2 (~43.96), TiO_2 (~0.06), Al_2O_3 (~1.92), FeO^T (~8.74), MnO (~0.12), MgO (~42.24), CaO (~1.80), Na_2O (~0.15), K_2O (~0.01), P_2O_5 (~0.01), in wt.%].

2. Synthesis Method

High-pressure experiments for both samples (No. I1565-1 and S7573) were performed using a multi-anvil press at the Bayerisches Geoinstitut, University of Bayreuth. The starting materials of I1565-1 and S7573 were loaded into a Pt capsule with outer and inner diameter of 1 mm and 0.8 mm, respectively, and sealed by arc welding. The capsule was then assembled within an MgO sleeve, a LaCrO_3 furnace, and put in a Cr_2O_3 -doped MgO octahedra with an edge length of 7 mm. The assembly was then compressed to the target pressure using tungsten carbide anvils with a 3 mm truncation edge length. Temperature was monitored with a D-type ($\text{W}_{75}\text{Re}_{25}$ - W_{97}Re_3) thermocouple for I1565-1 and a C-type ($\text{W}_{74}\text{Re}_{26}$ - W_{95}Re_5) thermocouple for S7573. The synthesis conditions were at 27 GPa / 2400 K for I1565-1, and at 24 GPa / 2173 K for S7573. The samples were quenched by cutting off electric power and subsequently decompressed to ambient conditions.

3. Major Elemental Compositions of the Synthesized Bridgmanite

- (1) I1565-1:** Stoichiometric MgSiO_3 bridgmanite.
- (2) S7573:** SiO_2 (~53.60), TiO_2 (~0.06), Al_2O_3 (~3.85), Cr_2O_3 (~0.53), FeO^T (~6.40), MnO (~0.11), MgO (~35.10), CaO (~0.25), Na_2O (~0.02), K_2O (~0.01), in wt.%.